

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TEST ANXIETY AND LEARNING PROCESS DISTRACTION IN PRIVATE SENIOR HIGH SCHOOLS

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The Relationship between Test Anxiety and Learning Process Distraction in Private Senior High Schools

Marc Niel P. Batingana*, Francis Micco Asumbrado, Samantha Llorin Del Prado, Resa Mae A. Ellorin,
Diana Rose M. Escabusa, Jeffrey P. Guimare II, Christyl C. Villaceran, Janine P. Rulona

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study determined the relationship between test anxiety and learning process distraction in private senior high schools. The descriptive research design was utilized and employed to the selected students through a survey with a total of 140 senior high school students as sample. Data Collection was done through a survey. Data analysis was done through mean, standard deviation, and pearson-r. Results revealed that the Level of of Test Anxiety with the mean of 3.22 and the Level of Learning Process Distraction with mean of 3.37 are all Moderately High, this means that item identified is sometimes manifested/observed. A positive correlation between the level of Test Anxiety and Learning Process Distraction in Private Senior High School was proven in the study. The findings affirmed that there is a significant relationship between the two variables.

Keywords: *test anxiety, learning process distraction, private senior high schools*

Introduction

Numerous studies have generated substantial evidence that distracted learning has quite a detrimental effect on learning (e.g., Fernandes & Mosocovitch, 2000; Foerde, Knowlton, & Poldrack, 2006; Glass & Kang, 2019; Jamet et al., 2020; May & Elder, 2018; Neiterman & Zaza, 2019; Paul, 2013; Rosen, Carrier, & Cheever, 2013; Sana, Weston, & Cepeda, 2013). Moreover, several investigations in the fields of neuroscience, cognitive science, and psychology have produced a vast body of research indicating that multitasking during academic work has a negative impact on students' performance and learning.

Several informational and recreational sources while completing homework, writing a paper, studying, or even in class (in person or virtually) has become a typical habit among youth. Increased accessibility to technology has resulted in a rise in diversions and distractions in daily living in today's tech-driven world. Particularly students are frequently distracted by technology in the classroom by playing games, purchasing online, and using social media. It might be difficult for teachers to identify instances in which students stray from the lesson plan, as when they participate in these distractions, and this can impede the learning process (Kiara Herro, 2023).

According to Aivaz and Teodorescu, 2022 states that distractions happen when someone chooses to work on multiple activities at once, as well as bits of unrelated information that we either find outside of ourselves or create ourselves. Interruptions that individuals attempt to execute multitasking is the term used to describe working on two or more independent goals at the same time.

Eman Dawood et al. 2016, states that test anxiety is a psychological disorder in which students suffer from extreme distress and anxiety when taking exams. Some students are more likely than others to experience test anxiety, particularly when juggling long study sessions that are necessary for success with multiple jobs, career adjustments, and family responsibilities.

There is a dearth of existing or similar study within the locality of Governor Generoso with regards to Test Anxiety and Student Learning Process Distraction of Senior High School students. This has motivated the researchers to come up with this study. Additionally, this research aim to determine physiological and psychological factors that cause severe test anxiety, particularly in senior secondary school students, as current research does not fully address these factors. This study is urgent to address the common difficulties experienced by the students that affect their learning process. Furthermore, the result of this study will add to the existing literature.

Research Objectives

The study aims to determine the relationship between test anxiety and student learning process distraction in private senior high schools. The following are the specific objectives.

1. To determine the level of test anxiety in terms of:
 - 1.1. fear of negative evaluation;
 - 1.2. negative thoughts; and
 - 1.3. communication apprehension.
2. To determine the level of learning process distraction in terms of:
 - 2.1. emotional distraction;
 - 2.2. digital addiction; and
 - 2.3. distraction by Procrastination.
3. To determine the significant relationship between test anxiety and learning process distraction in private senior high schools.

Literature Review

Test Anxiety and Learning Process Distraction

Learning distraction is anything that slows down, obstructs, impedes, or significantly diverts another process is commonly referred to as "interference," which also includes interruptions and distractions (Aivaz & Teodorescu, 2022). Additionally, interruptions happen when someone chooses to work on multiple tasks at once. Distractions are bits of unrelated information that we either encounter outside of ourselves or create internally. When neglecting to pay attention, there communication issues, slight distractions might result in accidents, and irresponsible reading may lead to misunderstanding (Cicekci & Sadik, 2019).

In addition, distraction is the process of taking someone's or a group's attention away from the desired focus, which prevents them from receiving the information they want (Soyemi & Soyemi, 2020). Goundar (2014) states that several academic employees stated that using personal laptops intensifying and disrupting the teaching and learning process in class (during lectures and tutorials when access to computers was not necessary). The actions of students and teachers, as well as the the learning atmosphere in the classroom distractions for learners that impair their ability to study (Najya A et al., 2017).

On the other hand, emotional distraction refers to the way that emotional diversion influenced the situations in day-to-day life. Distraction reduces negative feelings, according to prior studies (Ozawa et al., 2021). In addition, emotional distractions can originate from both our own thinking and external stimuli. Moreover, those involved in coping with it have received less attention than exterior emotional distraction, both of which have been the subject of substantial research (Lordan et al., 2018). Majority of the students said that they found it hardest to study at home. Parents should create a calm environment and acknowledge their children's need for ongoing emotional support as they transition into adulthood (Storm et al., 2023).

Pelham (2022) denotes that emotional distraction captures and maintains attention equally in both groups, surpassing cognitive control of attention and any bilingual benefits associated with that control. This could happen because the evolution of attentional systems that are readily and strongly engaged by emotional stimuli has resulted from the importance of emotional stimuli to survival; the capacity to ignore emotion may have been maladaptive and hence not selected for. According to factors that are now poorly understood, emotional inputs can hinder or improve task performance (Steward et al., 2023).

Distraction by Procrastination. Procrastination is the propensity to put off duties even when one is aware that doing so could have unfavorable effects. Previous research has demonstrated that procrastinating students have trouble focusing throughout the completion of tasks. These issues may stem from a reduced ability to resist distraction brought on by irrelevant cues that arise in the immediate surroundings (Wiwatowska et al., 2022). Procrastination is the propensity to put off duties while understanding that doing so could have unfavorable effects. Previous research has indicated that students who procrastinate regularly have trouble focusing on academics until it is finished (Wiwatowska et al., 2023).

According to Ojo, Students occasionally set aside time to finish their assignment but become sidetracked by other activities. These can be internal (their own ideas & urges) or external (Facebook, text messages, etc.) distractions (2019). Social media sites can be a distraction from personal, academic, and work-related duties. They can cause procrastinating behavior and harm students' academic achievement in a setting (Suarez et al., 2022). Sources of divergence that impair pupils' focus are WhatsApp messages, weariness and exhaustion, and a loss of interest in the activity's subject (Silva & Ramos, 2023).

Digital Addiction. Wang et al. said that the use of this technology enhances students' learning both inside and outside of the classroom in a variety of ways. Nevertheless, despite all of the advantages of technology, these online activities can also cause a lot of online distraction. Internet browsing, watching movies, checking texts, reading and sending emails, and browsing social media are just a few examples of digital distractions. Due to these constant digital distractions, students frequently pay less attention in class, are less engaged, and ultimately learn less and succeed less academically.

Digital distraction can be brought on by things like worry, melancholy, motivating factors, the need to keep up with others and the fear of being left behind, emotional numbness and procrastination, as well as an excessive reliance on multitasking (2022). Digital addiction is seen as a behavioral addiction, though there doesn't seem to be agreement on what it means exactly.

In addition, digital addiction has a variety of negative effects on the students, including behavioral, cognitive, and physical ones. Additionally, the excessive and compulsive use of digital technologies known as "digital addiction" can have a huge impact on society. These include the effects on social, economic, legal and ethical, educational, cultural and societal norms, healthcare, the environment, privacy, and security, as well as mental health (Şirin et al., 2023).

In higher education classrooms that allow the use of digital tools, digital addiction have grown more common as these devices become more and more commonplace in this globally connected world. When difficult material is presented with subpar pedagogy, digital distraction adversely affects students' capacity for cognitive processing, which impairs their ability to absorb information and develop schemas (Awofala et al., 2020).

However, digital addiction is limitless everywhere. They might be used by kids at anytime and anyplace to play video games, browse social media, and access the Internet. Young learners often become addicted to using their phones, playing video games, and using

social media because their minds are immature and hence extremely sensitive, leading to the problem known as "digital addiction" (Ding et al., 2023).

The rise of digital technology in the twenty-first century has led to discussions about digital addiction. The problematic use of digital gadgets (tablets, smartphones, etc.) that is typified by being excessive, compulsive, impulsive, and hasty is referred to as "digital addiction." Internet addiction, game addiction, cyber relationship addiction, information overload, social media addiction, wifi addiction, nomophobia, FOMO, and netlessphobia are just a few examples of the many addictions and diseases that fall under the category of digital addiction, which is a sort of behavioral addiction (Atasever et al., 2023).

Test Anxiety

The focus on the evaluative context of test anxiety, also known as examination anxiety, exam stress, and test stress, sets it apart from other anxiety expressions. Additionally, it was stated that test anxiety refers to negative physiological, emotional, and cognitive reactions to a test or assessment. Symptoms of test anxiety include rapid breathing and heartbeat, worry about performing poorly, and other symptoms that typically happen before, during, or after an assessed performance (Pachaiappan et al., 2023).

Test anxiety is described as the stress that builds up in the mind, body, and behavior in anticipation of receiving a poor grade on an exam, test, or other event involving an evaluation (Mels et al., 2023). Anxiety is characterized by worry, anxiety, boredom, and the thought that something horrible will happen at any moment. In addition, It is an emotion that arises from within for an unexplained reason (Uluyol et al., 2023). Stress and anxiety are difficult conditions that cause disruptions in the body's equilibrium. One's equilibrium on a bodily and mental level is disturbed (Daulatabad et al., 2023). The term "test anxiety" refers to a particular kind of anxiety that is felt during tests, exams, and other comparable testing circumstances that measure one's performance (Tan et al., 2023).

Communication Apprehension. Everyone is impacted by the problem of communication apprehension (CA). Everyone has some degree of public speaking anxiety, which is accompanied by emotions of timidity, anxiety, and tension. A higher percentage of CA, which causes acute anxiety in communicative circumstances and negatively affects scholastic performance and sociability. Everyone is impacted by CA, which has received substantial research. These uneasy sensations might happen in many different contexts (Dalan, 2023).

People's perceptions of the four types of communication—interpersonal or dyadic communication, small-group communication, meetings, and public speaking—are crucially influenced by CA (Booncherd & Rimkeeratikul, 2017). The concept of communication apprehension (CA) affects everyone. Every person, to some extent, experiences the fear of speaking in front of others or in interpersonal situations, along with the accompanying trepidation, uneasiness, and anxiety (Bragg, 2017). Every person experiences some level of communication apprehension (CA), and the degree of fear can either positively or negatively affect an individual's capacity for performance (Petry, 2016). Fear or anxiety related to actual or prospective communication with one or more people is known as communication apprehension (CA) (Rombalski, 2021).

Negative Thoughts. Things that pop into our heads suddenly and frequently out of our conscious control. These typically gloomy, self-critical, and negative thoughts can significantly affect our mood, conduct, and general well-being (Rasool, 2013). Negative thoughts are an inherent component of human cognition. However, for those who are dealing with mental health issues, such beliefs are frequently deeply ingrained, instinctive, and emotionally upsetting, making it challenging to dispel them at the time (Sharma et al., 2023). Furthermore, unwanted negative thoughts are defined as an uncontrollable train of thoughts that are frequently repetitious and emotionally taxing. They could stem from a person's dysfunctional attitude toward oneself and other people. It makes their sense of social isolation even worse (Lacy, 2022).

Automatically pessimistic thoughts begin to dominate the mind. Positive or negative themes could be included in those recurrent thoughts. The schemas that are produced by automatic thoughts are crucial for a person to construct their own world, comprehend the people around them, and comprehend their surroundings (Direktor, 2017). Students frequently experience negative thoughts, which have a negative effect on their academic performance, quality of life, and mental health. Therefore, it is essential to put in place interventions that deal with the root causes of worry and negative thinking as well as offer students social support (Saddique et al., 2023).

Fear of Negative Evaluation. Other researchers believed that worry of receiving a bad review may be factored into the measuring of social anxiety. As a separate component from social anxiety, poor evaluation (Liu et al., 2020). In addition, Fear of Negative Evaluation (FNE) the uncertainty regarding opinions of others, anxiety over their aversion to evaluative circumstances, negative judgments, and the anticipation that one would get unfavorable judgment from others (Leighton, 2018). The fear of being rejected by others due to body image, anxiety, and fear of negative evaluation on the basis of appearance rose as an adolescent when surrounded by peers who reported more body change and excessive weight loss behavior. Concern about having a poor impression of one's appearance by others has also been linked to low self-worth. Fear of negative evaluation is the feeling of being uneasy about receiving a bad evaluation (Gerada et al., 2020).

Moreover, according to several studies, boldness and fear of criticism go hand in hand. An adverse association between these variables was discovered in the study of Azer (2020). Fear of unfavorable evaluation, according to the study, suggested a belief about being

negatively assessed by others. The core personality trait of neuroticism, which measures how responsive one is to potentially dangerous stimuli and how frequently one experiences stress, includes negative appraisal and social anxiety (Randelović & Đorić, 2017).

Parents' Expectation. Parental expectations are developed as ambitions that are regulated by external forces, obstacles to participation, and other influences on both parents and student, such as risk perceptions or student personality qualities (Dockery et al., 2022). However, It has been shown that parents' expectations have a big impact on how well their learners do in school. Students with high expectations from their parents do better in school, get better marks, and stay in school longer than students with low expectations from their parents. Furthermore, it appears that parental expectations in terms of academic performance regulate the association between family background and achievement; high parental expectations also tend to mitigate the effects of low professor expectations on student achievement (Sadeghi, 2022).

Additionally, student's behavior is influenced by their parents' academic standards, which also help them succeed in school and in life. According to the expectation effect idea, as a malleable psychological state, human expectations not only encourage but also have an impact on other people's conduct (Xu et al., 2022). As opposed to what parents actually expect their children to do, parental aspirations often refer to demands, wishes, or goals that parents have developed regarding their children's future accomplishments (Haider, 2022) consequently, they believe it will help their child succeed in the future, many parents often want their children to perform better than everyone else in school. To succeed in life, however, they will need more than just good grades; they also need a positive attitude and self-control (Francis et al., 2020).

Methodology

Research Design

The researchers employed the quantitative non-experimental design method of research using correlation technique. They utilized descriptive-survey research to identify The Relationship Between Test Anxiety and Students Learning Process Distraction in Private Senior High Schools. This was an appropriate method wherein the researchers were able to gather data about the relationship between the said variables, Test Anxiety, and Students Learning Process Distraction.

Participants

The researchers conducted the study at Maryknoll High School of Sigaboy, Incorporated; Informatic Technology College of Davao Oriental; and Governor Generoso Agricultural Vocational Institute of Technology. The participants of this study were the senior high school students because the researchers intended to look into and ascertain the connection between the students' test anxiety and students learning process distraction. Also, not included in this study were the elementary pupils, elementary teachers, junior high and senior high teachers, administration, and school staffs. Students who refused to participate in answering the questionnaire were excluded. Moreover, they were free to withdraw from their participation in the conduct of the study if they found the questions that made them uncomfortable. Their personal reasons and well-being were highly prioritized by the researchers. Hence, the researchers were the ones to determine the appropriate number of samples in this study.

Instruments

The researchers made use of downloaded survey questionnaires. There were two sets of questionnaires adapted from different authors which were modified by the researchers and used to obtain information on the test anxiety and student learning process. The survey questionnaires that had been developed were validated by the experts. In order to give the respondents ease and comfort in answering each question and understanding the purpose of the study, the questionnaire was developed in a highly complete form with the assistance of the professional validators.

The first set of the questionnaire was the test anxiety with indicators such as fear of negative evaluation, negative thoughts, and communication apprehension. This instrument was adapted from the study of Hanane Bouhafs (2016). This part had a total of 8 items.

The second set of the questionnaire was the learning process distraction with indicators such as emotional distraction, digital addiction, and distraction by procrastination. This instrument was adapted from the study of (Awofala et al., 2022). This part had a total of 8 items.

All items were evaluated on a 5-point Likert scale with the rating of 5 strongly agree; 4 as agree; 3 as moderately agree; 2 as disagree; and, 1 as strongly disagree.

Procedure

In this study, the necessary data were gathered through systematic procedures. Survey questionnaires were disseminated to the respondents which contained the level of test anxiety and students learning process distraction among senior high schools. The following technique was used by the researchers to acquire information for this study.

First, the researchers wrote a permission letter addressed to the School Director. Moreover, the researchers wrote a letter to conduct the study to the School Director to allow the researchers to conduct the study to all senior high school students in the context of private

schools in Governor Generoso, Davao Oriental.

Furthermore, the researchers disseminated a consent letter to the respondents who were under the senior high school students to give authorization that they were the participants of the study. The questionnaires for Test Anxiety and Student Learning Process Distraction were distributed and administered by the researchers after they received authorization. As soon as participants completed their survey forms, the researchers personally retrieved the questionnaires and compiled all of the information, which was tallied by the statistician; confidentially and appropriately.

Ethical Considerations

Voluntary Participation and Privacy and Confidentiality. The respondents' participation in the study was completely voluntary and anonymous to protect their privacy. If they had any questions about what they were being asked to do, they were given the opportunity to ask for an explanation before they decided whether or not to participate.

No one, with the exception of the researcher, knew the names of the respondents or the specific responses each one provided. Participants and responses were given descriptions of the study's objective and the connections between its variables. Accordingly, the respondents were required to submit their questionnaires to the researchers after they were retrieved from their operating systems.

Additionally, participants were advised to decline to respond to questionnaire questions if doing so made them uncomfortable. They were also advised not to write their names, decline to write their responses if they did not understand the questions, and decline to respond if the questions were disrespectful or unachievable. The opportunity to drop out of the study as a respondent was made available by the researchers, and doing so came with no consequences or loss of study advantages.

Informed Consent Process. If participants were selected, the researchers explained to them the importance of their voluntary engagement and why they met the criteria for study informants' inclusion. Additionally, the respondents were given enough time to read the information provided in exchange for their voluntary participation and were given the opportunity to ask any concerns they might have had regarding the study's methodology.

Since the respondents expressed no concerns or reluctance about taking part in the survey, the data gathering procedure was finished right away, and the findings were announced as soon as they were ready. The chosen respondents' willingness to complete the survey questionnaires at a time that was convenient for them and consistently available to them, as well as the method of conducting the study, were both things that the researchers sincerely valued.

Recruitment. Prior to performing their research, the researchers got approval from the Maryknoll High School of Sigaboy, Inc. to the principal's office and the high school students. Once authorized, the letter of endorsement was given to the researchers as the go-ahead to distribute the survey questionnaires to the study's participants.

Risks. If any aspect of the risks or risk assessment associated with this research that survey participants were unsure about, it was the researchers' responsibility, as researchers, to obtain additional assistance and become familiar with the health and safety policies of the research location prior to completion.

The researchers clarified that participation in a research study had no adverse effects on the participants and that any risk or benefit that may have resulted from participating in the study was explained to prospective respondents before they agreed to take part. Respondents of a research study benefited from their involvement in that as well.

Benefits. The following were some ways that the respondents gained from this study: they were given the chance to express their freedom of speech and expression; they were able to express and rate themselves using the provided questions; the questions helped them carefully consider themselves; participants could privately assess their mental well-being and academic motivation; and the responses of the respondents influenced the research's findings. All of the children at Maryknoll High School of Sigaboy, Inc. received crucial knowledge from this research. Teachers and students could use the study's conclusions, justifications, and research findings to create and carry out interventions and solutions because they offered considerable proof.

Plagiarism. The researchers took care to properly credit all of the sources they used. To avoid the appearance of plagiarism, the writers' thoughts were skillfully paraphrased and synthesized throughout the study. This essay was looked at from a grammar teacher's perspective, which involved proofreading and ensuring that it didn't contain any plagiarized text.

Fabrication and Falsification. The results of this study were mostly dependent on the data that had been gathered, and the paper did not contain any inconsistencies with the body of recent literature. No data, insights, or characterization techniques that were not there at the time the data were collected were faked or replaced. Only conclusions based on the results of their research were produced by those working in this sector.

Conflict of Interest and Deceit. Researchers came to the conclusion that everyone had conflicts of interest, rendering them ultimately meaningless. It was possible to think of a comparable approach as a kind of beneficial comparison. This category of researchers defended their conduct by contrasting them with those of other researchers who were also involved in conflicts of interest. Finally, some people could express skepticism regarding the presence of conflicts of interest in the examples given. This method exhibited a

full disregard for the results of one's activities as well as the possible awareness of many conditions that could be detrimental. As a result, the survey participants in this instance were not directly under the researcher's control.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results of the data to determine the Relationship Between Test Anxiety And Learning Process Distraction Among Private Senior High School.

In Table 1 below, the level of Test Anxiety among Private high Senior High School in Governor Generoso Davao Oriental has a weighted mean of 3.22 with descriptive equivalent of moderate high which means that the item identified is often manifested/observed. Among the Three indicators in it (Fear of Negative Evaluation, Negative thought, Communication Apprehension), Communication Apprehension got the highest weighted mean of 3.39 with descriptive equivalent of Moderately High which means that the item identified is often manifested/observed. On the other hand, Fear Negative Evaluation got the lowest weighted mean of 3.06 with descriptive equivalent of Moderately High which means that the item identified is often manifested/observed.

Table 1. *Test Anxiety*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive level</i>
Fear of Negative Evaluation	3.06	Moderately high
Negative Thoughts	3.22	Moderately high
Communication Apprehension	3.39	Moderately high
Overall	3.22	Moderately high

In Table 2 below, the level of personality among the Learning Process Distraction Among Private Senior High School in Governor Generoso Davao Oriental. Has an overall weighted mean of 3.37 with the descriptive level of Moderately high which means that the item identified is often manifested/observed. Among the three indicators in it (Emotional Distraction, Digital Addiction, Distraction by Procrastination), Digital Addiction got the highest weighted mean of 3.41 with descriptive equivalent High which means that the item identified is often manifested/observed. On the other hand, Emotional Distraction got the lowest weighted mean of 3.31 with descriptive equivalent of Moderately High which means that the item identified is often manifested/observed.

Table 2. *Learning Process Distraction*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive level</i>
Emotional Distraction	3.31	Moderately High
Digital Addiction	3.41	High
Distraction by Procrastination	3.39	Moderately High
Overall	3.37	Moderately High

In Table 3 below are the result of the test of the Relationship Between Test Anxiety And Learning Process Distraction Among Private Senior High School, The relationship is not significant if the f-value is more than 0.01. Reflected on the table below, Test Anxiety And Learning Process Distraction has an f-value of 0.01.

Table 3. *Correlation Analysis of the Variables*

		<i>Test Anxiety</i>	<i>Learning Process Distraction</i>
Test Anxiety	Pearson Correlation	1	1.000**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.01
	N	2	2
Learning Process Distraction	Pearson Correlation	1.000**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.01	
	N	2	2

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

This means that there is no significant Relationship Between Test Anxiety Learning Process Distraction. In this representation, Test Anxiety is not significantly affected by students' personality, thus Rejecting the null hypothesis.

Test Anxiety

The level of test anxiety derived from the responses is moderately high. This connotes that the level of test anxiety in private senior high schools is sometimes manifested/observed. The indicators fear of negative evaluation, negative thoughts, communication apprehension, and parent's expectation were described as moderately high. Pachaiappan et al., 2023, stated that test anxiety refers to negative physiological, emotional, and cognitive reactions to a test or assessment. Symptoms of test anxiety include rapid breathing and heartbeat, worry about performing poorly, and other symptoms that typically happen before, during, or after an assessed performance.

Moreover, Test anxiety is described as the stress that builds up in the mind, body, and behavior in anticipation of receiving a poor grade on an exam, test, or other event involving an evaluation (Mels et al., 2023). Hence, Test anxiety (TA) refers to the enduring inclination

to experience an exaggerated emotional reaction during academic evaluations, driven by apprehensions about underperforming and potential adverse outcomes (Balogun et al., 2017; Putwain & Symes, 2018).

Learning Process Distraction

The level of learning process distraction derived from the responses is moderately high. This connotes that the level of test anxiety in private senior high schools is sometimes manifested/observed. Previous research has indicated that students who procrastinate regularly have trouble focusing on academics until it is finished (Wiwatowska et al., 2023).

Emotional Distraction

Emotional Distraction is described as moderately high in this study and therefore is sometimes manifested/observed. Emotional Distraction refers to the way that emotional diversion influenced the situations in day-to-day life. Distraction reduces negative feelings, according to prior studies (Ozawa et al., 2021).

Digital Addiction

Digital Addiction is described as high in this study and therefore is often manifested/observed. Past studies on technology addiction among students revealed that they acknowledged the problem of internet addiction and admitted to skipping classes and delaying tasks because of their uncontrollable use of technology (Hafit et al., 2021).

Distraction by Procrastination

Distraction by Procrastination is described as moderately high in this study and therefore is sometimes manifested/observed. Previous research has indicated that students who procrastinate regularly have trouble focusing on academics until it is finished (Wiwatowska et al., 2023). Moreover, Previous research has demonstrated that procrastinating students have trouble focusing throughout the completion of tasks. These issues may stem from a reduced ability to resist distraction brought on by irrelevant cues that arise in the immediate surroundings (Wiwatowska et al., 2022).

Significance of Relationship between Test Anxiety and Learning Process Distraction

The test of the relationship between variables revealed that there was a strong and positive significant relationship between test anxiety and learning process distraction in private senior high schools. This implied that any adjustment on the level of test anxiety has a corresponding effect on the level of learning process distraction.

Students with test anxieties usually have trouble studying and get distracted during exams. Long study periods, higher university dropout rates, exam failures, as well as physical and psychological problems are a few outcomes of test anxiety. Test anxiety is influenced by a variety of things. The inability of students to improve their learning and their impression of their knowledge have both been identified as factors affecting students' achievement and stress levels (Yusefzadeh et al., 2019).

Moreover, Examination stress, particularly worry, significantly impacts academic achievement and working memory. According to Okonkwo (2022), examination stress diminishes attention span, memory, and concentration, ultimately leading to lower academic success. Numerous studies by researchers have also confirmed that high school students with high levels of examination stress tend to perform poorly in school.

Additionally, examination stress is believed to hinder some individuals from reaching their academic potential. Explanations for this connection include a tendency to dwell on and fret over exams, as well as a propensity to be more easily diverted. Concern about exams was associated with susceptibility to learning distraction, but not exactly as expected. Nevertheless, both fretfulness and a tendency to be diverted by non-threatening, exam-irrelevant material were found to forecast academic performance. These findings are considered in the context of theories of test anxiety, as well as the potential for additional research and interventions to address learning process distraction.

Conclusions

The data obtained for this study was analyzed and found to be adequate to support the following conclusions. The level of Test Anxiety and Learning process distraction is moderately high. This means that test anxiety and learning process distraction is sometimes observed in many occasions by the private senior high school students.

Moreover, there is a significant relationship between test anxiety and learning process distraction among private senior high schools. There is a positive relationship between Test Anxiety and Learning process distraction. This signifies that test anxiety is correlated with learning process distraction.

Based on the results of this study, the researchers came up with suggestions and recommendations for future reference and for the future researchers.

Firstly, studying in advance is a good technique to avoid test anxiety because an individual practices preparing himself for the upcoming exams. Additionally, it is important that students who take the exam have taken good notes for studying. This technique will lessen the

burden of the students to avoid last-minute preparation. Unavailability of good notes depicts low performance during the test or examinations.

This study is limited to the sample size. Hence, future research may consider including a more diverse group of private senior high school students in terms of demographic characteristics such as gender, age, socio-economic background, and academic performance to ensure the results are more representative and generalizable. Future research may delve on topics such as time management, responsibilities, status in life, and the like as determining factors of test anxiety.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Marc Niel P. Batingana

Maryknoll School of Sigaboy, Inc. – Philippines

Francis Micco Asumbrado

Maryknoll School of Sigaboy, Inc. – Philippines

Samantha Llorin Del Prado

Maryknoll School of Sigaboy, Inc. – Philippines

Resa Mae A. Ellorin

Maryknoll School of Sigaboy, Inc. – Philippines

Diana Rose M. Escabusa

Maryknoll School of Sigaboy, Inc. – Philippines

Jeffrey P. Guimare II

Maryknoll School of Sigaboy, Inc. – Philippines

Christyl C. Villaceran

Maryknoll School of Sigaboy, Inc. – Philippines

Janine P. Rulona, MAED

Maryknoll School of Sigaboy, Inc. – Philippines